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**DEVELOPMENT BY ROBOCASTING AND MECHANICAL
CHARACTERIZATION OF HYBRID HA/PCL COAXIAL SCAFFOLDS FOR
BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS**

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Abstract

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4 Porous structures consisting of a tetragonal three-dimensional mesh of interpenetrating coaxial tubes
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6 were fabricated by robocasting from hydroxyapatite (HA) inks. After sintering the structures,
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8 polycaprolactone (PCL) was infiltrated within the tubes core by injection of a polymer **solution**. The
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10 addition of the polymer enhanced the mechanical performance in terms of toughness over dense- and
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12 hollow-strut all-ceramic scaffolds, specially **under bending stresses**. **PCL impregnation improved also**
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14 **the compressive strength over hollow-strut scaffolds** —although dense-strut structures remained stronger
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16 especially in compression. Thus, this coaxial core-shell strut configuration combines the best features of
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18 each material: the necessary stiffness and excellent osteoconductivity of the bioceramic, with the high
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20 toughness and ductility of the biopolymer; and allows the fabrication of hybrid scaffolds with the
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22 interconnected macroporosity necessary for cell ingrowth. Hence, this work successfully provides a
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24 proof-of-concept of this novel strategy for the mechanical enhancement of bioceramic-based scaffolds
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26 **while preserving their osteoconductive properties**.
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51 **Keywords:** Coaxial scaffolds; Robocasting; Mechanical properties; Hydroxyapatite; Polycaprolactone.
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1. Introduction

Development of biomaterials with similar properties to bone is essential to solve the limitations associated with the currently available procedures for repairing bone lesions: autografts are associated with a limited amount of available material and the need of secondary surgical sites, allografts mean a risk in terms of immunogenic response and disease transmission, and the use of artificial ‘bioinert’ prosthesis often cause bone resorption, leading to implant loosening and subsequent replacement surgeries [1]. Scaffolds, porous structures fabricated from ‘bioactive’ materials, and tissue engineering offer a suitable alternative [2]. In contrast to the aforementioned prosthetic devices, ‘bioactive’ scaffolds are capable to interact with the surrounding tissue and actively induce bone in-growth. ‘Bioactive’ ceramics (calcium phosphates, calcium sulfate, etc.) and bioglasses (45S5, 13-93, 6P53B, etc.), thanks to their similar composition to the inorganic-phase of bone, exhibit excellent osteoconductivity [3] and can be biodegradable and osteoinductive [4]. Unfortunately, they are also mechanically weak and extremely brittle materials [5,6]. The strength of active bioceramic and bioglass scaffolds fabricated by conventional techniques, such as gas foaming or foam replication, can barely reach cancellous bone values [7], and remain far from cortical bone performance. Such low strength, together with their intrinsic brittleness, relegates their application to regions of the skeleton exposed to low levels of stress [5,6].

Using Additive Manufacturing (AM) techniques, such as robocasting [8,9], it is possible to obtain porous structures with any desired external shape and a controlled pore architecture. Robocasting (a.k.a. direct ink writing) is a material extrusion process consisting on the robotic deposition of water-based ceramic inks layer by layer, forming a network of interconnected rods which can be easily used to develop porous biodegradable scaffolds [10] from various calcium phosphates [8,9,11] and bioglasses [10–13] The great microstructural control provided by robocasting (and other AM techniques) facilitates

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4 creating porosities with the required level of interconnection to permit the transport of nutrients, cells,
5 and vessels [14,15], at significantly reduced total porosities, which translates into dramatically improved
6 performances in terms of strength [16,17]. In spite of that, the application of these structures in load-
7 bearing regions of the skeleton is still prevented by the intrinsic brittleness of 'bioactive' ceramics and
8 bioglasses.
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11 Accordingly, many recent studies have focused on adding a biodegradable polymeric phase to improve
12 the toughness of bioceramic scaffolds, either by fully impregnation or simply coating [18–24] (Fig 1a,b).
13 Despite the unquestionable enhancement of the mechanical properties achieved through these strategies,
14 they also involve evident drawbacks in terms of the biological performance, such as the loss of the
15 bioceramic osteoconductive surface, and even the blockage of the entire porosity of the structure when it
16 is fully-impregnated (Fig 1a). Even if those characteristics might be eventually recovered after
17 implantation as the biodegradable polymer is resorbed, they can obviously retard scaffold's
18 osteointegration, tissue regeneration and overall healing process. As an alternative approach, in this
19 work the fabrication of porous structures with composite struts consisting on an outer bioceramic shell
20 and a polymeric core (Fig 1c) is proposed as a means to overcome the previously mentioned limitations.
21 This novel disposition should still combine the best mechanical features of both materials, the stiffness
22 of the bioceramic and the toughness of the polymer, without losing either the osteoconductive surface of
23 the bioceramic nor sacrificing the interconnected porosity required for bone ingrowth.
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26 Consequently, this study seeks to provide a proof-of-concept for this novel hybrid ceramic/polymer
27 scaffold architecture by fabricating simple structures consisting of an outer hydroxyapatite (HA) shell
28 and a polycaprolactone (PCL) core. For this purpose, HA scaffolds with hollow rods are fabricated by
29 robocasting, using a coaxial nozzle for extrusion. After sintering, the internal channels of the rods are
30 infiltrated with PCL solutions with the help of a syringe. Although there are a few examples of coaxial
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4 extrusion in robocasting [25–28] and on the fabrication of scaffolds with hollow struts [28–30], and even
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6 some on impregnation of said scaffolds with polymers [22,23,31], for the first time the impregnation is
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8 made selectively to avoid the presence of polymer on the external surface of the hollow struts. Uniaxial
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10 compression and 3-point-bending tests are used to mechanically characterize the samples, in terms of
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12 strength and toughness, with the aim of providing valuable insight into the mechanical behavior of this
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14 novel hybrid robocast scaffolds for bone-tissue engineering applications.
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23 **2. Materials and methods**

24 *2.1. Fabrication and microstructural characterization*

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27 A water-based ink with a solid content of 45 vol.% was prepared from commercially available HA
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29 powder (HA Captal[®] S, Plasma Biotal, North Derbyshire, U.K), with a particle size (D_{50}) of 3.83 μm .
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32 Firstly, to obtain a stable suspension, 1.5 wt.% (relative to powder content) of Darvan C dispersant (R.T.
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34 Vanderbilt, Norwalk, CT) and the HA powder were mixed in distilled water, in this order. Then, 7
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36 mg/ml of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (Methocel F4M, Dow Chemical Company, Midland, MI) was
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38 added to increase the viscosity of the suspension. Finally, the addition of 4 vol.% (relative to liquid
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40 content) of polyethylenimine (PEI) flocculated the mixture to obtain the required rheological behavior—
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42 extrudable but capable of supporting its own weight upon deposition— of a robocasting ink. The mixing
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44 of the components was made in a centrifugal planetary mixer (ARE-250, Thinky Corp., Tokyo, Japan)
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46 after each addition.
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55 A syringe was, then, partially filled with the fabricated ink, and tapped vigorously to remove air bubbles.
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57 The syringe was placed in a robocasting device (Aerotech A3200, 3-D Inks, Stillwater, OK) controlled
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59 by a computer-aided program (Robocad 4.2.9, 3-D Inks). To construct, layer by layer, a log-pile
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4 structure of hollow rods, a coaxial needle (Linari Engineering S.R.L., Pisa, Italy), with outer internal
5 diameter $d_e = 1.37$ mm, and inner external diameter $d_i = 0.83$ mm was used. The deposition was
6 performed at room temperature in a paraffin oil (Ceragi, Gerona, Spain) bath to avoid uneven drying,
7 and the same oil was forced to circulate through the innermost channel of the coaxial needle while the
8 ceramic ink was co-extruded through the outer channel (Fig. 2) at a constant printing speed of 40 mm/s.

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17 Scaffolds consisting on a tetragonal network of HA tubes—comprising layers of parallel tubes disposed
18 orthogonally to adjacent ones— were, thus, fabricated (Fig. 3a). The spacing between tubes in each
19 layer was chosen to be $s = 2.5$ mm, and the distance between the center of tubes in adjacent layers or
20 layer height was $h = 1.1$ mm. A total of 7 layers were deposited to construct the scaffolds with external
21 dimensions 45 x 45 x 7.7 mm. In addition, scaffolds with dense bars were also fabricated for
22 comparison, using conventional nozzles (EFD Nordson) with a diameter of 1.37 mm. Two different
23 designs were considered in the fabrication of these scaffolds: in the first one, designated from now on
24 with a 0 subscript, layers were disposed so that tube in-plane positions were coincident in all parallel
25 layers (Figure 3b), while in the second design the rods in parallel layers are offset 50% (represented with
26 50 subscript) of their in-plane center-to-center separation distance, s (Figure 3c). These were used to
27 determine the optimal configuration for the tubular scaffolds.

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45 Printed scaffolds were dried at room conditions for one hour and, then, sintered in air using the
46 following heat treatment: an intermediate plateau at 800 °C for 2 hours to eliminate the organics
47 additives in the ink, followed by sintering at 1300 °C for 2 hours, using a constant heating rate of
48 3 °C/min and free-cooling at the end of the sintering treatment. This treatment provided optimal
49 mechanical performance for the selected material without altering its phase composition, according to
50 preliminary studies.

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4 After sintering, a biodegradable polymer, polycaprolactone (Capa 6500, Perstorp Holding AB, Malmö),
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6 with a mean molecular weight of 50kDa was used to fill the internal channels of the scaffold tubular
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8 struts. For this purpose, solutions of PCL in toluene were prepared at 60 °C with two different
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10 concentrations: 15 vol.% and 30 vol.%. After loading the selected PCL solution on a syringe, every tube
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12 in the structure was manually injected using a needle (gauge 27, EFD Nordson) smaller than the inner
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14 tube diameter until completely filled, when the polymeric solution emerged from the side opposite to the
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16 syringe. After letting the sample for 24 h at room temperature to ensure full evaporation of toluene
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18 solvent, HA/PCL hybrid scaffolds with tubes partially impregnated with different amounts of PCL were
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20 obtained. Thus, scaffolds with hollow (H), infiltrated (I: 15-I and 30-I) and dense (D: D₀ and D₅₀) rods
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22 were fabricated. Microstructural features of those scaffolds were observed in a scanning electron
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24 microscope, SEM, (S-3600 N, Hitachi, Japan) and their mean internal dimensions were measured from
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26 these SEM images. Finally, the apparent density of each scaffold was estimated from measurements of
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28 the weight and external dimensions of the specimens.
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38 *2.2. Mechanical testing*

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40 Uniaxial compression tests were performed on a universal testing machine (AG-IS10kN, Shimadzu,
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42 Kyoto, Japan) in air and with a constant crosshead speed of 0.6 mm/min to determine the compressive
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44 strength of hollow, infiltrated and dense rods specimens with as-cut external dimensions of around
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46 $5 \times 5 \times 6 \text{ mm}^3$. Tests were performed with the loading axis normal to the printing plane (z direction in
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48 Figure 2), and in the case of dense-rod scaffolds some samples were tested also parallel to one of the
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50 rods directions (direction x and y in Figure 2). For each configuration (designated by \perp or \parallel superscripts,
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52 where necessary) and sample type a minimum of 8 specimens were tested, and the corresponding
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54 nominal stress-strain curves obtained after normalization of registered load-displacement data using
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4 each sample's initial dimensions. The compressive strength (σ_c) of each specimen was determined as the
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6 maximum **peak** stress in the curve and the average value and corresponding standard deviation was
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8 evaluated for each condition. Concerning toughness, strain energy densities (G) were calculated as the
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10 area under the stress-strain curves up to a strain of 0.4 ($G_{0.4}$).
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15 Three-point bending tests were also conducted on the same testing machine in air, but at a constant
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17 crosshead speed of 6 mm/min. A minimum of 8 **cut** specimens with external dimensions of around
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19 **25 × 5 × 6 mm³** were tested applying the load perpendicular to the printing plane. Load-displacement
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21 curves were registered and the flexural strength (σ_f) was calculated from the maximum load, F_{max} , in
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23 each curve using the following equation [19]:
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$$\sigma_f = \frac{3 L F_{max}}{2 w t^2}$$

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32 Where $L = 20$ mm is the distance between the support cylinders, and w and t are specimen's width and
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34 thickness, respectively. Strain energy density (G) was calculated as the area under load-displacement
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36 curves divided by the volume of the sample between the supports. In particular, the area was evaluated
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38 up to a maximum displacement of 4 mm (G_4).
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47 **3. Results and analysis**

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50 SEM micrographs from cross-sections views of the fabricated scaffolds (with a 0%-offset design) are
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52 shown in Figure 4. In these micrographs it is evident that hollow rods (Figs. 4c,d) preserve their round
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54 shape— **any differences observed with their dense counterparts (Figs 4a,b) are within variability of**
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56 **measured dimensions**—with no visible collapse but some small flattening at the contact with adjacent
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4 rods. Moreover, in the case of scaffolds infiltrated by 30 vol.% PCL solutions (Figs. 4e,f) it is noticeable
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6 how a significant portion of the volume of the channels is occupied by the polymer. However, the
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8 occupation is not complete **nor completely homogeneous** and large pores or a small central channel can
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10 still be observed in the core of these hybrid struts, as a result of solvent evaporation. The level of
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12 occupation is obviously lower when 15 vol.% solutions are infiltrated, but the polymer still coats the
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14 internal surfaces of the tubes. Mean dimensions for scaffolds with hollow (*H*) and infiltrated (*I*) rods, as
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16 measured from SEM images, are as follows: external rod diameter, $d_e = 1.28 \pm 0.06$ mm; internal
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18 diameter, $d_i = 0.54 \pm 0.04$ mm; spacing between rods, $s = 2.3 \pm 0.2$ mm; and layer height,
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20 $h = 0.94 \pm 0.03$ mm. **Geometrical calculations using these measurements yielded a pre-defined**
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22 **macroporosity of 42 ± 12 % (excluding the inner channel of the struts, which amount to an additional**
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24 **$\sim 11 \pm 3$ % macroporosity) and density measurements found tube walls to be 73 ± 6 % dense (considering**
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26 **a theoretical density for HA of 3.16 g/cm³) after sintering, so microporosity was also abundant, as**
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28 **evidenced in the SEM images of Fig. 4.** In case of scaffolds with dense rods (*D*), dimensions were
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30 $d_e = 1.20 \pm 0.03$ mm, $s = 2.17 \pm 0.02$ mm and $h = 0.95 \pm 0.02$ mm. The apparent density measured in *H*
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32 samples, $\rho_a = 0.85 \pm 0.03$ g/cm³, is obviously lower than the corresponding value for *D* samples
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34 (1.14 ± 0.05 g/cm³) but the gap is bridged after polymer impregnation (0.96 ± 0.03 g/cm³ for *15-I*
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36 samples, and 1.06 ± 0.07 g/cm³ for *30-I*). There is, thus, an increase in the amount of PCL infiltrated
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38 into the structures as the concentration in the solution increases. **A quick calculation taking into account**
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40 **the theoretical density of polycaprolactone (1.145 g/cm³) shows that PCL occupied 10 ± 5 % and 18 ± 9**
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42 **% of the scaffold volume, depending on the concentration of the PCL solution.** Since the central
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44 channels occupied only **$\sim 11 \pm 3$ % of the volume, PCL** must have impregnated also part of the tube walls
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46 microporosity, at least for the higher concentration, in order to account for the observed density
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48 variations. **This is in good accord with SEM observations (Fig. 4f) where polymer microfibrils could be**
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4 observed sticking out of the ceramic walls' micropores near the internal channel after cutting. However,
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6 the occupancy estimations and SEM observations suggest that impregnation of the walls microporosity
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8 was not complete.
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12 To determine the best scaffold design, preliminary uniaxial compression and 3-point bending tests were
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14 first conducted on dense-rod scaffolds. The mechanical behavior under compressive stresses of D_0 and
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16 D_{50} samples was tested under normal (\perp) and parallel (\parallel) configuration. The average compressive
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18 strength values evaluated for each configuration are shown in Fig. 5a. No statistically significant
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20 ($p > 0.05$) differences were observed between the compressive strength of both designs for specimens
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22 tested along the rods' axes (16 ± 5 MPa for D_0^{\parallel} and 14 ± 4 MPa for D_{50}^{\parallel}). However, the result under a
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24 load normal to the printing plane resulted to be dramatically higher in the scaffolds with no offset (D_0^{\perp} ,
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26 13 ± 3 MPa) than in the 50% offset design (D_{50}^{\perp} , 1.8 ± 0.4). This is explained by the fact that in D_0
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28 samples continuous columns of material, formed by the intersections between rod layers, support the
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30 compressive load, while in the design of D_{50} the load produces pure bending in the perpendicular rods
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32 and the ceramic material fails promptly under this most deleterious loading mode. Based on these results
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34 it is evident that the zero-offset is the most convenient design against compressive loads, with strengths
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36 slightly superior, on average, to cancellous bone values. The situation does not change in bending, as
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38 shown in Fig. 5b, where the zero offset structure exhibit strength values 40% higher than the 50 % offset
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40 design. Consequently, the effect of the new coaxial strut configuration and of polymer infiltration
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42 conditions was carried out using only samples fabricated with the zero-offset design and applying the
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44 load orthogonal to the printing plain since it is the weakest configuration in compression.
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56 To analyze the damage modes generated during uniaxial compression in each type of sample, *in-situ*
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58 images were taken during the tests, and representative sequences are shown in Figure 6. As observed in
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4 the figure, fracture initiates close to the intersection between rods, both in dense and coaxial (hollow and
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6 impregnated) structures. However, in the latter (*H* and *I*) it is impossible to determine whether this
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8 fracture initiates at the external surface of the struts, as is the case when struts are dense (*D*) [19,33,34],
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10 or at the internal channel surfaces. Besides, in hollow structures, the fracture is observed to occur layer
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12 by layer rather than propagating longitudinal cracks throughout the whole structure as in *D* structures.
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14 Also, while both hollow and dense rods samples are broken in shards at the end of the test (Figs. 6c and
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16 6f), the PCL-infiltrated samples remain mostly in one piece even after much larger compressive
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18 deformations (Fig. 6i) and preserve certain structural integrity.
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25 In good accordance with the *in situ* observations, the representative stress-strain curves (Figure 7a)
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27 registered during the tests reveal, how while dense-strut (*D*) samples collapse not long after reaching a
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29 clear initial maximum of the stress curve, samples with hollow struts (*H*) exhibit a sawtooth-like curve
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31 with successive peaks as the different layers fail, until it is totally destroyed, and maximum stress does
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33 not necessarily correspond to the first peak. Such layer-by-layer failure is also observed in PCL-
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35 infiltrated scaffolds (*15-I*, *30-I*). However, in the latter case, the polymeric phase inside the channels
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37 holds the broken ceramic tubes together and as the structure gets compacted, the load not only never
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39 drops to zero but increases progressively even after very large strains. The residual load-bearing
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41 capacity of the broken scaffolds clearly increases with the concentration of the polymer in the
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43 infiltrating solution, i.e. with the volume of polymer within the tubes.
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51 On the other hand, as shown in the bar chart of Fig. 7b, the compressive strength of *D* samples is nearly
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53 an order of magnitude higher than for *H* scaffolds (13 ± 3 MPa vs. 2 ± 2 MPa, respectively). **The**
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55 **compressive strength decrease was expected and strength values for *H* scaffolds are similar to those**
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57 **reported for other material compositions [26–28] . Fortunately,** infiltration with PCL can enhance both
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59 the strength and reliability of the scaffolds in compression. The increase in strength is moderate (37.5 %)
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4 in 15-I samples but nearly a factor of two (87.5 %) for 30-I hybrid structures. This strengthening is
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6 insufficient to bridge the gap with the dense-strut scaffolds and somewhat smaller than existing reports
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8 on fully coated structures [20,22,24,35,36]. However, it still yields structures with strength values
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10 clearly within cancellous bone range, and much greater reliability than the original hollow scaffolds. As
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12 discussed in previous works, the strengthening effect of polymer impregnation can have two origins:
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14 defect healing or stress shielding [20,37]. While a definitive prove would require a more exhaustive
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16 analysis of the stress fields in these coaxial structures, the only partial infiltration of the internal channel,
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18 the low modulus of PCL compared to HA, and the fact that reliability is so clearly improved, all point
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20 towards defect healing as the main mechanism of strengthening. That implies that fracture is initiating,
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22 due to a diametral compression of the tubes [38], at the internal surface of the coaxial channels where
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24 PCL can seal any fracture-precursor flaws. The sealing is, predictably, more effective at higher
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26 concentrations of PCL in the infiltrating solution.
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34 Finally, as in existing literature [22–24] polymer impregnation produces a substantial toughening of the
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36 scaffolds. As shown in Figure 7c, the strain energy density of infiltrated scaffolds at 0.4 strain is clearly
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38 superior to that of both hollow and dense scaffolds. Especially in the case of 30-I samples, in which
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40 impregnation improves energy density by a factor of 6 over *H* samples and triples the value of *D*
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42 specimens, approaching the range for natural bone. This is due to the presence of a continuous, ductile
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44 polymeric phase, which holds the structure together after the ceramic part fails and dissipates energy as
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46 it deforms. Another interesting result is that despite their nearly one order of magnitude superior
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48 strength, dense-rod scaffolds are not that much tougher (in terms of strain energy density) than their
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50 hollow counterparts, as a consequence of their more catastrophic failure. The more gradual failure of
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52 hollow-strut structures could be considered beneficial in terms of flaw tolerance, especially when
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4 combined with polymer impregnation, to provide a residual mechanical integrity after each cracking
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10 All in all, the preceding results clearly demonstrate that the proposed strategy of using hybrid scaffolds
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12 with core-shell ceramic/polymer struts is feasible for enhancing ductility of the bioceramic structures in
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14 compression, but at the expense of significant reduction of the scaffold strength compared to structures
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16 with dense struts. This compressive strength decrease, attributed to the diametral compaction of the
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18 tubular struts, can be reduced as the internal channel is filled with the polymer due to precursor defect
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20 healing. This weakening effect could be further reduced if a complete impregnation of the internal
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22 channel of the struts with the polymer was achieved. Using a stiffer polymer like PLA (or PEEK, if
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24 biodegradation is not required) for infiltration will also help reduce the deleterious effect of diametral
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26 compression by reducing the stresses acting on the tube wall, although at the expense of reducing
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28 ductility. Such stress shielding effect of polymer impregnation would be added to the defect healing
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30 strengthening mechanism already evidenced by the results of this work. Analyzing the effect of other
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32 polymer compositions and achieving full occupation of the internal channel by the infiltrating polymer
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34 will be the subject of future studies that are currently underway.
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4 Since diametral compression of the tubes is so deleterious, the proposed strategy could be even more
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6 effective under loading modes where compression is not dominating. Thus, three-point bending tests
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8 were also carried out in scaffolds with hollow, dense and infiltrated rods, but this time using only the
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10 most concentrated PCL solutions (30-I) since the advantages of greater polymer concentrations has
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12 already been demonstrated. The optical sequences of Figure 8, taken *in-situ* during these flexural tests,
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14 show the typical brittle fracture in both *D* and *H* samples, although fracture is more abrupt in *D*.
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16 However, in 30-I samples long after the ceramic shells fracture, the PCL filaments are still capable of
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18 bridging the crack walls together by stretching out to very large strains (Fig. 8i).
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25 The different fracture behaviors are even clearer on the representative load-stroke curves in Fig. 9a. In
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27 good agreement with the *in-situ* observations, *D* samples exhibit a classic brittle curve: linear elastic
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29 response up to a peak load, followed by a sudden load drop to zero upon fracture. On *H* samples the
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31 response is also brittle, but several consecutive peaks can be observed in the curve, evidencing that
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33 fracture occurs somewhat more progressively, in a layerwise manner. **This behavior had not been**
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35 **previously reported as in the scarce literature on hollow scaffolds mechanical characterization is limited**
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37 **to compression. Eventually,** load falls definitively to zero after all ceramic struts are broken. On the
38
39 contrary, hybrid 30-I samples can keep bearing load after the peak is reached, signaling the failure of the
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41 ceramic shells. After the maximum, the stress decreases gradually down to a plateau, and that residual
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43 load bearing capacity and the mechanical integrity of the part are maintained even after very large
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45 deflections.
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52 On the other hand, the results in Fig. 9b show that, unlike in compression, the bending strength remains
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54 unchanged upon PCL infiltration (i.e. no statistically significant differences are found between the
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56 average values for *H* and 30-I samples). This reflects the fact that now fracture initiates at the external
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58 surfaces of the struts and, thus, the polymer within the channels cannot seal the precursor flaws in this
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4 case. Moreover, no significant stress modifications (i.e. stress-shielding) are expected due to the
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6 presence of the polymeric core, since even when the central channel is filled with the much stiffer HA,
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8 the strength differences are under 33%. In any case, for the selected scaffold design and material system
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10 used in this study, the mechanical performance in terms of bending strength is still far from natural bone
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12 performance. Fortunately, there is ample room for improvement both in the design and materials sides,
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14 since this is just a first proof-of-concept study in which none of these aspects was sought to be
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16 optimized.
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22 While polymer impregnation does not produce strengthening of the tubular-strut scaffolds under bending
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24 stresses, its effect is dramatic in terms of toughening of the structure. Due to the crack-bridging effect of
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26 PCL fibres, the strain energy density of hybrid 30-I scaffolds is one order of magnitude higher than in *H*
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28 samples ($G_4 = 0.07 \pm 0.04 \text{ MJ/m}^3$ vs. $0.006 \pm 0.005 \text{ MJ/m}^3$), as shown in Fig. 9c. And, contrary to
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30 compression, *G* under bending stresses in dense samples is lower than in *H* samples, despite their greater
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32 strength, since the layer-by-layer fracture observed in *H* samples allows them to survive greater strains.
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34 Despite this notable toughening, comparable to that obtained in fully coated/impregnated structures, the
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36 measured values are still far from the fracture energies of natural bone. Nonetheless, the achieved
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38 performance is an outstanding result considering that, unlike in previous reports on infiltrated robocast
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40 scaffolds [19,21], the 30-I scaffolds preserve intact a macroporosity of around 50 %, and that the
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42 impregnation of the strut channels by PCL is not complete. Moreover, this level of toughening is
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44 achieved on a system exhibiting flexural strengths lower than previously reported robocast
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46 composites [19,21], and despite the lack of strengthening produced by the polymer impregnation
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48 (Fig 9b), as the bioceramic external surfaces remain pristine and free of polymer. All these
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50 considerations suggest that further mechanical enhancements will be attainable through further
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52 optimization of the infiltration process—to achieve a full impregnation of the internal channel and
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4 produce scaffolds with dense polymer/ceramic core/shell struts—, scaffold design (e.g. channel diameter
5 and morphology, struts shape, etc.) and material system—to enhance the intrinsic performance of the
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7 structures. Thus, the results of this study are encouraging as they imply that the selected toughening
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9 strategy is extremely successful, especially against the most deleterious bending stresses. Further studies
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11 along this research avenue are, thus, guaranteed, **in order** to optimize the mechanical performance. **Also,**
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13 **although there is abundant evidence in the literature on the advantages of a bioceramic surface over most**
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15 **typical biopolymers in terms of biological performance [40,41]. In fact, addition of bioceramic particles**
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17 **is a typical strategy to improve the osteoregenerative properties of biopolymers [42–44], it will be**
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19 **necessary to** verify that the biological behavior of the proposed core/shell hybrid scaffolds is as good as
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21 anticipated. **Performing suitable biological *in vitro* (dissolution and mineralization, cell culture, etc.) and**
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23 **also *in vivo* tests should be the focus of future work on this research line.**
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32 **4. Conclusions**

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34 Concerning scaffold design, the study performed indicates that non-displaced layers, D_0 , results in
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36 improved performance both in compression and bending compared to the 50 %-offset configuration,
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38 D_{50} , and the results confirm that loading perpendicular to the printing plane is more deleterious than
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40 along the rods axes [22]. On the other hand, hollow rods HA scaffolds have been successfully fabricated
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42 by robocasting in this work using coaxial extrusion. After sintering, the fabricated structures maintain
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44 intact their intra-strut channels, enabling their infiltration of PCL solutions with a concentration up to 30
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46 vol.% via injection. After solvent evaporation a major portion of the channel volume is occupied by the
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48 polymer. The mechanical performance of the hollow-strut scaffolds is enhanced with the addition of the
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50 polymer. Strength is improved in compression and remains unaltered in bending, although, they both
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52 remain below the levels achieved in scaffolds with dense rods of similar external diameter. However, in
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54 terms of toughness, polymer infiltration improves the performance well over both types of all-ceramic
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4 scaffolds. The enhancement is especially remarkable under bending stresses, where results for hybrid
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6 scaffolds are one order of magnitude higher than for the rest of structures studied in this work.
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8 Moreover, the proposed core/shell hybrid structures, unlike other toughening strategies, should be able
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10 to preserve intact both the osteoconductive properties of the bioceramic material and the scaffold
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12 macroporosity necessary for cell ingrowth. Thus, this work successfully provides a proof-of-concept for
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14 this novel core/shell hybrid scaffold architecture, which shows great promise for the mechanical
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16 enhancement of bioceramic-based scaffolds without jeopardizing their biological performance.
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Figure 1. Schematic of different alternatives for the fabrication of ceramic (gray) / polymer (blue) composites through polymer impregnation of robocast scaffolds: (a) fully-impregnated, (b) coated and (c) core/shell structures.

Figure 2. Robocasting process of scaffolds constructed layer by layer with a coaxial tip. A 3-axis robotic system moves the injection syringe while pressing the ceramic-ink, and the paraffin oil is simultaneously extruded to obtain hollow-rods scaffolds.

Figure 3. Schematic of different scaffolds designs fabricated by robocasting: (a) dense without offset, (b) dense with 50 % offset between parallel layers, and (c) hollow without offset.

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of cross-sections of representative scaffold struts: (a, b) dense (c, d) hollow and (e, f) infiltrated with 30%-PCL solutions.

Figure 5. (a) Compressive strength for all **dense** designs and load configurations, as indicated. (b) Bending strength values for both designs. Data represent mean values, with standard deviations as error. Typical values for human cancellous bone [32] are shown as a shaded band for comparison.

Figure 6. In-situ optical sequences taken during uniaxial compression tests on HA scaffolds with (a-c) dense rods, (d-f) hollow struts, and (g-i) struts infiltrated with 30% PCL solutions.

Figure 7. (a) Representative strain-stress curves and average values of (b) compressive strengths and (c) strain energy densities at 0.4 strain for *D*, *H*, *15-I* and *30-I* specimens, as evaluated in uniaxial compression tests. Error bars represent standard deviations. Typical values for human bone [32,39] are shown as shaded bands.

Figure 8. In-situ image sequences of *D* (a-c), *H* (d-f) and *30-I* (g-i) samples during 3-point-bending tests. Inset in (i) shows polymeric fibers generated during fracture of *I* samples at higher magnification.

Figure 9. (a) Representative load-stroke curves, (b) flexural strengths and (c) strain energy densities for *D*, *H* and *30-I* specimens under 3-points-bending tests. Average values with standard deviations as error bars are shown in (b) and (c). Typical values for human bone [21,32,39,45,46] are shown as shaded bands for comparison